
ICT USAGE OF ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE LIBRARIES IN ERODE DISTRICT – A STUDY

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Abstract:

The targets of this observe is to analyse the existing collections, ICT infrastructure and services , opportunities of introducing useful resource sharing and networking Activities amongst libraries, and to reveal the ICT abilities amongst Librarians in 23 Arts and Science College libraries in Erode District, Tamil Nadu. Questionnaire technique became used to gather the specified information and Simple random sampling approach turned into used to examine the amassed facts.

Keywords: *ICT skills, ICT centres, Networking, Resource Sharing.*

Introduction:

Resource sharing and networking has altered the old idea of due to the multi-dimensional and multi directional enlargement of published documents, enlargement of present day era for facts processing and dissemination, growing price of books and periodicals are a number of the essential aspects which require statistics Resource sharing and networking the various libraries. Along with that getting into inter-library mortgage practice, libraries notion intensely of useful resource sharing and networking for the spread of records which is the final results of the rapid boom of courses and staying within the poor price range they may be trying to include libraries cautiously for aid sharing of their precept of collection improvement. the libraries are not organized and fully equipped to render services to the users satisfactorily should be taken care of.

Modern information technology has made the activity of resource sharing very simple and convenient manner. This new technology comes forward for products and services of the library that have changed the traditional library and operation which may be called the revolutionary changes to the information field.

Objectives:

- To look into the existing collections, ICT infrastructure and offerings provided by means of arts and Science College Erode District.
- To identify the ICT centers of the university libraries in Arts and science faculties in Erode District.
- To have a look at the ICT talents amongst Librarians running in university libraries Arts and technology colleges in Erode District.

Review of the Literature:

Veena G (2016)¹ The most important reason of this have a look at is to research the awareness and usage of open get right of entry to digital information sources and related problems among put up graduate students of Mangalore University. A questionnaire-based totally survey technique has been used in this studies. A overall of 180 questionnaires allotted but 152 were again duly crammed in as a pattern. The findings indicates that 72(forty seven.36%) of respondents frequently used e-books/ e-journals, 58(38.15%) of respondents received their open get right of entry to e-resource utilization talent through instructors/research supervisors, ninety eight(64.47%) of the respondents said that they're happy with open access e-assets. The end result of the take a look at shows that majority of students are aware about open get right of entry to e- assets.

Doraswamy Naick (2016)² This paper is explain Networking of Engineering College. Libraries Affiliated to JNTU, Kakinada in Andhra Pradesh: A Prototype Design based on Information Seeking Behaviour of Faculty. The examiner states that most of the faculty contributors are widely known the networking version and few of them expected to use the information retrieval. Majority of the team of workers participants guide the prototype model evolved by the researcher.

Santhi & Nagarajan (2015)³ The paper offers the results of a look at on the impact of open get entry to resources on coaching and research in engineering faculties, Puducherry. Eleven schools were selected. The statistics were accumulated the usage of questionnaire by way of census approach. The take a look at found out that stage of awareness and use of

open access sources is as much as the expectancies. The college students are exceedingly happy with the open access sources utilized by the school for dealing with instructions. The respondents additionally faced a few constraints which have been highlighted.

Mothukuri Anjaiah (2014)⁴ The Internet is a prime resource of verbal exchange and distribution of information inside the 21st century. Nowadays the Internet has an important detail in educational institutions because it will become a critical position in dealing with the statistics and verbal exchange necessities of establishments. The paper examined that the big variety 93 (seventy four. Forty four%) of the school individuals and research pupils had been acquire the records through the internet for teaching and research manner, maximum of the respondents sixty four(fifty one.2) retrieving the e-information from college library and maximum of the respondents fifty two (41.6%) are virtually satisfied with using UGC-Info-net e-journals and they have provided 1st rank to American Institute of Physics , 2nd rank to American Institute of Society on the basis of utilization).

Siddike and Kalam 2012)⁵ Describes the customers perceptions on networking and useful resource sharing amongst a number of the academic libraries in Bangladesh, with information on common facts-looking for behavior in the academic institutions. Objectives containing the demand for Modern Information Technology centers by means of the researchers at instructional agencies, the shortage of good enough data sources and inefficiency of the interlibrary resource sharing system were analysed and concluded.

Suhyeon Yoo (2010)⁶The take a

look at investigates few of the contemporary demanding situations and useful resource sharing activities in Korea, specifically from the viewpoints of the functions of country wide and worldwide group libraries in Korea.

Methodology:

The literatures to be had at the title has been studied and reviewed to research the useful resource sharing and networking activities a few of the 23 Arts and Science College libraries in Erode District. The properly- structured questionnaire become organized covering all of the info of the targets and sent it to the 23 libraries to gather the facts. Collected number one information became tabulated and analyses by using the easy random sample strategies.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Collections of books

Sr. No.	Collections	No. of Libraries	Percentage
1	Below 25000	5	21.74
2	25001 - 50000	8	34.78
3	50001 - 75000	3	13.04
4	75001 - 100000	5	21.74
5	above 100000	2	8.7
Total		23	100

Table-1 shows the collections of printed book in the college libraries. Majority of the college's libraries has 25001 - 50000(34.78%) books for circulation followed by 21.74% of the colleges has below 25000. Among that 3 libraries has 50001 - 75000 and only 2 libraries has more than one lakhs books for circulation. This table indicates as no library is sufficient in terms of quantity and quality of collection and as such the

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collections available in management college libraries calls for resource sharing and networking.

Table 2: Services offered by the library

Sr. no.	Services	No. of Libraries	%
1	Circulation of books	23	100
2	Referral Service	22	95.65
3	CAS	19	82.61
4	Reprography service	15	65.22
5	Book Bank service	16	70
6	Catalogue service	20	87
7	Reference services	17	74
8	User education	21	91.3
9	Inter library loan	5	22

Table 2 shows that hundred percentages of the libraries circulate the books to their users. Majority of the libraries offered current awareness service, Reference Catalogue service etc., and 91.3 percentage of the libraries conduct the User Education/ orientation programmed to their students to use the library user-friendly. Some of the libraries provided the Referral Service (74%), Book Bank service (70%), Reprography service (65.22%) respectively. Very few of the selected libraries exchange the books to inter library loan (22%).

Table 3: ICT facilities in libraries

Sr. No.	Description	Yes	%	No	%
1	Online Database services	8	34.78	20	86.95
2	E - mail	21	91.3	5	21.74
3	Digital Library Services	22	95.65	4	17.39
4	Institutional Repository services	7	30.43	18	78.26
5	Web - OPAC	2	8.69	19	82.6
6	Ask Librarian	3	13.04	21	91.3
7	CD - ROM Database services	19	82.6	15	65.21

8	Newspaper clipping services	20	86.96	7	30.43
9	Internet services	22	95.65	8	34.78

The table 3 defines that most of the libraries having ICT facilities like E-mail (91.3%), news paper clipping services (86.96%), Digital Library Services (95.65%), CD ROM Database services (82.6%), and Internet services (95.65%) respectively. Some of the libraries having minimum level of ICT facilities such as Online Database Services (34.78%), Institutional Repository Services (30.43%), Web-OPAC (8.69%), Ask Librarian(13.04%).

Table 4: Skills of the librarians

Sr. no.	Skills	High	Medium	Low
1	Library automation	15 (65.22%)	10 (43.48%)	5 (21.74%)
2	Institutional Repository	13 (56.52%)	9 (39.13%)	6 (26.09%)
3	Operating system	20 (86.95%)	15 (65.22%)	7 (30.43%)
4	Network Technologies	12 (52.17%)	8 (34.79%)	4 (17.39%)
5	Office automation	21 (91.30%)	17 (73.91%)	11 (47.83%)
6	Web Technologies	9 (39.13%)	7 (30.43%)	3 (13.04%)

Table 4 explains that most of the librarians having the high level skills for Office Automation (91.30%). It is followed by operating system (86.95%) and library automation (65.22%), followed by Network Technologies (52.17%), Institutional Repository (56.52%) and least importance has been given to web technologies (39.13%).

Table 5: Willingness to Library Resources and Networks

Willingness	No. of Colleges	Percentage
Yes	14	60.87
No	9	39.13
Total	23	100

Table 5 shows that 60.87 % of libraries are willing to participate in there sources having Library Network and 39.13% are not willing to participate in the Library Resource Sharing and Networking programme.

Conclusion:

The study shows that the prevailing collections are very low for the expectation stage of customers and the libraries will give a boost to the collections. The offerings furnished by way of the library is not sufficient the e book financial institution service, inter library mortgage service, reprography carrier etc., need to be accelerated. The have a look at recommends that librarians of the pattern libraries should replace their modern-day tendencies in ICT skills. Most of the librarians are consent to proportion the assets and networking centres available in the libraries. , to improve the triumphing negative services, care have to without delay be taken to provide efficient resource sharing systems among the libraries thru better control and use of present day technological facilities. Thus, it's far important to take important moves to create an green internet-working and resource sharing device a few of the libraries for imparting superior offerings to the customers of the district.

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